

BatoLabo, a travelling laboratory exploring waterways through the arts, the humanities and citizenship

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How is a river doing? The question may seem strange. Yet today it lies at the heart of much scientific research and community-led initiatives. In France and across Europe, researchers, artists and local residents are experimenting with new ways of understanding and protecting river ecosystems. This concern is of particular importance in the European context, where rivers have undergone, over the last two centuries, profound changes to their morphology and a massive deterioration in the quality and diversity of their biotopes (Linton, 2010; Petts, 1989; Tockner et al., 2009; Vörösmarty et al., 2010).

Among these initiatives, several projects complement and extend one another along the Loire, notably the collective 'Vers un parlement de Loire', the various editions of 'La Grande Remontée de Loire', and the recognition of Loire nautical knowledge as part of the Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH). It is within this dynamic that the scientific and artistic expedition BatoLabo emerged, a travelling laboratory from the Loire to the Danube. This river laboratory invites us to rethink the way in which human societies observe, narrate and care for rivers through a scientific protocol and artistic interventions that contribute to the Fluvioscope research project, supported by the National Network of Houses of Social Sciences and Humanities (RnMSH) and coordinated by the MSH Val de Loire alongside six other MSHs (Alsace, Ange-Guépin, Claude-Nicolas Ledoux, Clermont-Ferrand, Paris-Nord and Mondes).

Navigation as a methodological approach to breaking down barriers between fields of knowledge

Navigation, aboard a heritage boat on the Loire (La Fillonnerie), forms an integral part of the method for engaging with riverine territories and their inhabitants. This unique approach shines a spotlight on waterways and the challenges they face, highlights the connections between fragmented river systems, and links different river cultures with as many traditions, practices and forms of knowledge as there are regions explored.

On board, research takes a different form: by sailing, meeting local residents, and sharing knowledge across disciplines and with the general public, particularly through outreach events such as the study day 'The Call of the Rivers', organised on 17 October 2025 in Nanterre with MSH Mondes, Paris Nord and Val de Loire, or the Strasbourg workshop on 2 April 2026 entitled "River health: a new issue for the humanities and social sciences", organised by MISHA in partnership with MSH Val de Loire as part of the Fluvioscope project.

There is a wealth of scientific knowledge about rivers, but it often remains distant from the general public or riverside communities. Conversely, residents and users of rivers also possess valuable knowledge: navigation practices, field observations, memories of floods or changes to the landscape. Researchers refer to the 'plurality of knowledge' to describe this diversity of scientific, technical, local or experiential knowledge. The workshops, residencies and meetings organised as part of Fluvioscope and BatoLabo aim to create spaces for dialogue between these different forms of knowledge. This approach falls within the field of environmental humanities, a research strand that combines the natural sciences and the humanities to better understand changes in living systems. Beyond the production of knowledge, these initiatives invite a broader reflection led by the Collectif Vers un parlement de Loire: how can human societies live with rivers rather than simply exploiting them?

Here, navigation does not serve as a vehicle for tourism or leisure, but rather as a vehicle for exploration, within which spaces for experimentation and storytelling are developed. The data

produced constitutes a mixed corpus (interviews, audio recordings, graphic illustrations, photos, DNA samples, etc.) that can be used for scientific, artistic and educational purposes. BatoLabo explores a co-production of knowledge from the river environment, paying particular attention to the sensory. This expedition embodies a vehicle for fostering a connection to the river environment, with the aim of generating an 'emotional buzz' (Sébastien, 2022) during which powerful new collective emotions are forged through the intertwining of past, present and future relationships with the watercourse. Thus, we propose that emotions should not be viewed as an obstacle to rational thought, but as a means of acquiring knowledge and understanding from river environments.

This desire to bring different perspectives together reflects an idea that is increasingly prevalent in the humanities and social sciences: understanding a river is not limited to analysing its physical or biological parameters. One must also take into account the cultural, social, political and historical relationships that link it to human societies. For several decades, environmental policies have focused primarily on water quality or ecological restoration. These actions remain essential, but they are not sufficient to transform the relationships between societies and their natural environments. The Fluvioscope approach therefore calls for 'caring for rivers' and broadens this perspective. It involves viewing rivers not only as resources, but also as living entities with which humans maintain multiple relationships.

An approach based on attachments to watercourses to examine the health of rivers

In collaboration with MSHE Ledoux researchers (Laure Nuninger and Cyril Masselot), BatoLabo is conducting an on-the-ground study (ReciTER) on attachments to watercourses, which feeds into the interdisciplinary reflection led by the Fluvioscope research project on river health. The concept of attachment involves understanding what we hold dear as inhabitants of the world in which we live. It allows us to start from what is experienced and felt in order to understand how this can generate a process of reciprocal acculturation rooted in the physical and heritage characteristics of the river environment. Thus, attachment would emerge from the private sphere to be put into words and into action through the collective co-production of a resource potentially capable of transforming our relationships with the world and with others, human or otherwise. This concept has generally remained in the shadow of research focused on adaptation to a world characterised by instability and change, which necessitates framing the problem in global terms.

Through this study, we analyse how residents express and narrate their attachment to the watercourse, whether positive or negative. The aim is to capture discourses based on what anchors us in a given place and time (anchor point), but also within the flow of residents' activities, whose lifelines intersect and intertwine with that of navigation, which itself flows with the moving watercourse (Ingold, 2007). In other words, we seek to identify the different forms of attachment to watercourses at the local level, but also within the perception of a riverine continuum (upstream/downstream), which itself forms part of a broader socio-hydrographic system. The survey 'from' the boat invites participants to make this shift in scale from the local to the global. Our aim is to highlight the forms of attachment that stem from a culture specific to each European territory traversed, as well as those that form part of a broader vision shaped by the territory specific to the watercourse, or even the water system to which it contributes.

The method involves implementing a research protocol based on a quantitative and qualitative scientific approach, paying particular attention to the sensory dimension, given the central role that attachment plays in our thinking and the cultural framework offered by BatoLabo from the watercourse:

- On attachment to the watercourse: meeting and listening to local residents, using a questionnaire-interview followed by discourse analysis, to understand what connects them to the watercourse in their area through their activities, memories, sensibilities and commitment(s).
- Through attachment to the watercourse (putting BatoLabo on the couch): each crew member will keep a daily logbook to engage in self-reflection regarding this river adventure.

- Through connection to the watercourse: providing a 'sensory kit' to those on board or encountered, to place them in the role of investigators with a view to collecting traces of this river journey.

This research protocol in the humanities and social sciences is complemented by a biological analysis of the algal communities inhabiting the waterways crossed, using environmental DNA sampling.

The samples are then analysed by teams at INRAE Thonon-les-Bains (UMR CARRETEL / University of Savoie-Mont-Blanc) to reinforce existing studies on phytoplankton diversity. These samples are taken every 30 km from the Loire estuary to the Danube delta, thus constituting the longest DNA transect ever carried out across Europe from west to east.

A contribution to the rights of nature

This expedition is closely linked to programmes such as Bourges, European Capital of Culture 2028, and the International Rivers initiative led by Camille de Toledo, as well as the European Citizens' Initiative 'Right of Nature', which is working to spark the necessary debate for its political implementation. This reflection is part of a broader international movement questioning the rights of nature. In several countries, certain rivers have already been granted legal personality to ensure their protection. These experiences are now fuelling debates across Europe. Engaging with the rights of nature allows us to explore new ways of thinking about the relationships between human societies and river environments, opening up scientific, legal, political and cultural perspectives to better understand and support the contemporary transformations of rivers. By linking the Loire, the Seine, the Rhine and the Danube, the researchers involved in these projects may be sketching out a new way of doing science: research that unfolds along the water's course, in close contact with the local areas and the people who live alongside living rivers.

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